

Teacher Education: A Need in Globalize Area (NEP)

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Abstract:

It is well known that teachers have a pivotal role in the development of an inclusive education system. Highly motivated, qualified, and trained teachers are important factor for ensuring meaningful access to education is the key for development of any nation and it depends on the quality of teachers. Knowledge, dedication, quality, professional commitment and motivation of teachers are the factors responsible for quality education and learner achievement. Producing such teachers is a major challenge for governments across the globe today. With the ever-increasing amount of knowledge today, teacher's job has been more challenging in the light of new pedagogical and psychological theories, philosophy, sociology and globalization. Well planned and imaginative Teacher education programmes are required today.

Teacher education programme has to be critiqued, studied, reformed, rethought and reoriented today. Improvement in teacher education is a 3-dimensional task. It's a challenge for every nation to provide well prepared and effective teachers. It is a well-known saying that teacher is the nation builder. The quality of teacher education programme needs to be up graded. Teacher education has not come up to the requisite standards. Teachers are not able to think critically and solve the issue related to teaching methods, content, organisation etc. teacher education programme needs a comprehensive reform and restructuring curriculum of teacher-education programme needs to be revised according to changing needs of society.

Keywords: *education, teacher education, issues, challenges*

Introduction:

The process of globalization has not only changed the social, economic, and cultural landscapes across the world, it has significantly affected the nature of geographic boundaries, national and international organizations, social institutions, individuals, as well as corporations. Successful navigation of such changes requires creation of high-quality human resources and the necessary education to meet such goals. Education systems worldwide are bracing themselves to cope with the burgeoning knowledge-based economy by identifying the need to prepare teachers who are

well-equipped to address context-specific challenges.

SES's Four-Year Integrated Teacher Education Programmes (ITEP), also called BA.B.Ed. programmes, aim to bring together multidisciplinary undergraduate education and professional preparation of school teachers. The programme envisions to provide excellent quality pre-service teacher education that addresses the longstanding issue of insufficient focus on disciplinary knowledge and lack of its integration with professional knowledge in teacher preparation in India.

Objectives:

1. To understand the meaning of education.
2. To understand the meaning of teacher education.
3. To understand the importance of teacher education.
4. To understand the ITEP.

Meaning of Teacher Education:

Teacher education refers to the policies and procedures designed to equip teachers with the knowledge, attitudes, behaviours, and skills they require to perform their tasks effectively in the school and classroom. In early times, teachers were often scholars or clergymen who had no formal training in how to teach the subjects of their expertise. In fact, many believed that "teachers were born, not made." It was not until the emergence of pedagogy, the "art and science of teaching," as an accepted discipline that the training of teachers was considered important. Although there has been continued debate about whether teaching is a "science" that can be taught or whether one is "born" to be a teacher, it has generally been agreed, at least since the nineteenth century, that certain characteristics are needed to qualify a person as a teacher: knowledge of the subject matter to be taught, knowledge of teaching methods, and practical experience in applying both. Most educational programs for teachers today focus upon these points. However, the internal character of the individual is also an important aspect of teaching; whether that is something one is born with or can be taught, and what are the qualities that are needed for the role of teacher, are also a matter of debate.

Goods Dictionary of Education explains-, „Teacher education means all the formal and non-formal activities and experiences that help to qualify a person to assume responsibilities of a member of the educational profession or to discharge his responsibilities more effectively.

“W.H. Kilpatrick specified teacher training by stating that „Training is given to animals and circus performers, while education is to human beings. Teacher education encompasses teaching skills, sound pedagogical theory and professional skills. Teacher Education = Teaching Skills + Pedagogical theory + Professional skills.

“Clinton stated in his Call for Action for American Education in the 21st Century (1996) that, “Every community should have a talented and dedicated teacher in every classroom. We have enormous opportunity for ensuring teacher quality well into the 21st century if we recruit promising people into teaching and give them the highest quality preparation and training”.

Significance of Teacher Education:

The ITEP or BA B.Ed. programmes at SES will prepare school teachers for two school stages based on the curricular structure proposed by the National Education Policy 2020 (5+3+3+4). These stage **Preparatory** (III to V) and **Secondary** (IX to XII) As dual major degrees, the programmes will offer the students a holistic undergraduate education equivalent to an undergraduate degree in selected areas of social sciences and humanities relevant for school teaching, as well as provide them the minimum qualification for school teaching at preparatory and secondary stages. These programmes include curricular

components based on the foundations of education, subject specialisation, pedagogy courses, ability enhancement courses, school experience and community engagement. The curriculum will be as per the norms of and regulated by the National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) has launched Integrated Teacher Education Programme (ITEP) in 57 Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) from the academic session 2023-24 throughout the country. This is a flagship programme of NCTE under NEP 2020. ITEP, as notified on 26 October 2021, is a 4 Year dual-major holistic undergraduate degree offering B.A. B.Ed./ B. Sc. B. Ed. and B.Com. B.Ed. This course will prepare teachers for the 4 stages of the new school structure i.e. Foundational, Preparatory, Middle and Secondary (5+3+3+4). The programme is being offered in pilot mode initially in reputed Central/State Government Universities/Institutions. ITEP will be available for all students who choose teaching as a profession after Secondary, by choice. This integrated course will benefit students since they will save one year by finishing the course in 4 years rather than the customary 5 years required by the present B.Ed. plan. Admission for the same will be carried out by the National Testing Agency (NTA) through the National Common Entrance Test (NCET).

ITEP will not only impart cutting-edge pedagogy but will also establish a foundation in early childhood care and education (ECCE), foundational literacy and numeracy (FLN), inclusive education and an understanding of India and its values/ethos/art/traditions, among others. The course will contribute substantially to the revitalization of the

whole teacher education sector. The prospective teachers passing out of this course through a multi-disciplinary environment, grounded in Indian values and traditions will be instilled with the needs of 21st century global standards and, hence, will be the harbingers in shaping the future of New India council for Teacher Education, that has granted recognition to SES to offer the programmes is a comprehensive four-year undergraduate programme that emphasizes a dual-major approach, and seamlessly integrates teacher education within the broader higher education system. Set to commence from the academic session of 2023-24, it offers students the opportunity to pursue Bachelor of Science (B.Sc.) with Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.), or Bachelor of Arts (B.A.) with B.Ed., or Bachelor of Commerce (B.Com.) with B.Ed. Students enrolled in this programme will complete their studies within a condensed timeframe of four years, as opposed to the conventional five-year duration mandated by the current B.Ed. Curriculum. ITEP will be available for all students who choose teaching as a profession after passing the exit examination of Higher Secondary (10+2) in any discipline (Humanities/ Science/ Commerce/ Others). The National Testing Agency (NTA) will be responsible for conducting the admission process for the programme. This will be done through the administration of the National Common Entrance Test (NCET). ITEP marks a significant an educational institution performs a significant function of providing learning experiences to lead their students from the darkness of ignorance to the light of knowledge. The key personnel in the institutions who play an important role to bring about this

transformation are teachers. As stated by NCTE (1998) in Quality Concerns in Secondary Teacher Education, –The teacher is the most important element in any educational program. It is the teacher who is mainly responsible for implementation of the educational process at any stage. || This shows that it is imperative to invest in the preparation of teachers, so that the future of a nation is secure. The 2 importance of competent teachers to the nation 's school system can in no way be overemphasized. The National Curriculum Framework 2005 places demands and expectations on the teacher, which need to be addressed by both initial and continuing teacher education. milestone in the field of teacher education.

Challenges against Teaching:

Improper and inadequate practice teaching Generally practice teaching is not taken seriously and professionally by pupil teachers, especially in many private teacher training institutes and there is a lack of sense of duty, and they remain irresponsible, aimless, and indifferent to children, which are hurdles in the development of pedagogical skills. Lack of subject knowledge The B.Ed. programme does not emphasize the knowledge of the basic subject. It should ensure the development of subject knowledge along with teaching skills. Without it the teaching practice will remain somewhat ineffective with regard to the subject knowledge. Inappropriate methods of teaching In India teacher educators are neutral towards adopting innovative methods and experimentation in their teaching. Their acquaintance with modern class-room technologies and effective ICT techniques is poor. Incomplete

supervision and feedback the supervision coupled with proper feedback is useful for improving practice teaching and instructional activity of the pupil teachers. Feedback and support help them in developing confidence to face the classroom. Guidance for planning lessons, learning to organize contents, and developing other classroom skills are its parts but in reality, the lesson plans are checked superficially and no meaningful discussion is made by the subject method masters.

Incompetent teachers and students:

Today the organizers of teacher's training programme/institutions are not well aware of the actual and practical problems of schools. The training programmes being provided are not properly framed, and do not to give opportunities to the students and teachers to develop required teaching competency. Actually, there should be a connection between the work schedule of the teacher who is in the programme and school that is being adopted for teacher preparation in a training college

Inappropriate Teaching Practice:

Teaching practice being provided in teacher training institutions is neither adequate nor properly conducted. Although, all kinds arrangements regarding practice in teaching are elaborated yet today student teachers do not take the task of teaching seriously. The big obstacles in the development of pedagogical skills are deficient in sense of duty, irresponsibility, aimless, lacking innovative measure in teaching etc

Lack of subject knowledge:

Today's teacher training programme does not lay emphasis on the knowledge of the basic subject. During the whole process of teaching practice, the

student teacher remains indifferent with regard to the subject knowledge. Even while supervising the teaching practice sessions no subject expert is provided to give feedback that is required for specific subject.

Inappropriate teaching method:

In India teacher educators are reluctant to testing and upgraded or new teaching methods. They are less acquainted with communication devices and technological changes coming across the modern class-room. Neither any training is being provided to student teachers to use new technology in their classrooms nor are they stimulated to do so.

Isolation of Education Departments, colleges and Institutions:

The teacher education has become isolated from schools. The current development in school education has been observed separately by education commission. In the real sense teacher education department should be treated as the nursery for the professional development of school teacher but the fact is something else, the schools consider these institutes as an alien. Nor the education departments are serious to treat the school teachers as their product. Both these departments i.e. education department and schools are not caring for the sounders of pedagogy involved in the procedure. Yet both are busy in only observing the formality of completing the prescribed number of lessons.

Faulty supervision:

The supervisory organizations for practice teaching should aim at guiding the pupil teachers in learning to organize contents, planning their lessons, developing other related skills and formulating suitable gestures. At present

their lesson plans are checked superficially. There is less opportunity for the students to discuss their lesson plans with some subject method specialist. Most of the time is spent on teaching session and less to the feedback session. While maximum time should be spent on discussion about the positive and negative aspects of pupil teacher's performance while practice.

Inadequate number of teacher educators:

The above problem of lack of proper supervision is due to the shortage of good teacher educators. Number of teacher educators is very less as compare to the required ones. Many colleges do not appoint sufficient number of teachers.

Changing qualifications of the teacher educators:

From last 20 years qualifications and eligibility criterion for appointing teacher educators is changing frequently. With every change level of qualifications is going low. By lowering the qualifications how can we expect to get teachers of higher quality?

Inadequate empirical research in education:

No Quality research is now being done in the field of education. Whatever research is being conducted is of either of poor quality or is not of practical use. Before undertaking any research, the teacher programmes are not studied properly.

Poor academic performance background of student teachers:

Mostly candidates getting admission in teacher training programmes are of poor academic background. They are not internally motivated to choose this profession. Thus,

have low background for a well-deserved entry in the teaching profession.

Poor physical conditions:

In India, the teacher education programme never has been placed at its deserving position yet always has to face step motherly treatment. Many of the teacher education institutions are being run in rented buildings. Many are running are without proper facility of an experimental school or library or laboratory and other equipment's, which are necessary for a good teacher education department.

B. Solutions to overcome the challenges Training of in-service teacher educators:

At this level teacher education need to work for the teacher educators who are already working in government and private teacher education institutions but are not well versed with the new trends of education. To deal with this situation's teacher education should provide various programmes. A few of these can be as follows:

Training courses:

In government sector, there are many in service programme being run by the educationa institutions to improve the level of teaching of in-service teachers. Due to privatization number of private colleges is much higher than government. But no programmes are being organized to train the teacher as well as teacher educators working in private colleges. The provisions should also be there for training of the teachers working in private sector also.

Supervision of teacher educators:

Unlike government institutions, in private institutions also there should be some system like API, through which

progress and further learning of teachers can be assessed. There must be some areas in which supervision should be there that can motivate all the teachers and teacher educators to work from their heart.

Incentives for the teacher educators:

Some incentives should be offered to the teachers either monetary or in the form of awards or appreciations by which the teachers can be motivated to do their work from the core of their heart.

Timely updating of curriculum**Proper monitoring of private institutions****Development of critical thinking****Development and enrichment of life skills****Developing competency of teachers****Maintaining Academic Uniformity****Conclusion:**

Teacher and his education are very significant aspects of any nation. The education gives a new shape to the individual and the nation as well. No doubt a lot of stress is given on teacher-education course in India. Unfortunately, still there are several loopholes in the system.

Teacher education is a difficult assignment, especially at the present stage where teacher education programmes are being delivered by a large number of unaided private teacher education institutions. These institutions are also not sure of their tenure, as in near future; possibility of huge unemployment of trained persons may result in swinging fall. The surviving institutions can only be helped by appropriate authorities in improving quality of their academic management. This paper suggests an increase in responsibility for teachers but

not an increase in authority: teachers are losing decision-making authority in the classroom. This paper also indicates that a positive policy environment and ample support for growth are essential for creating and sustaining teacher quality.

References:

1. Afshan Anees (2015),” Teacher Education and their Problems”, “ International Journal of Academic Research in Education and Review
2. Imam Ashraf (2011) Quality and Excellence in Teacher Education:

Issues & Challenges in India. International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research

3. Behera Rashmi, Ranjit Bera: “Fundamental of teacher education”, Redshine publication.
4. Prof Shukla Anil, Dr. Varma Anupama: “Fundamental of ITEP “, Astitva Prakashan.
5. <https://pib.gov.in>
6. <https://itep.iitbbs.ac.in>
7. <https://www.theyogicjournal.com>
8. <http://shreeprakashan.com>